

DIPHENYLCARBAZIDE AND DIPHENYLCARBAZONE. PART I. THEIR ESTIMATIONS

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A method for the estimation of diphenylcarbazine and diphenylcarbazone has been developed with ferric iron as the oxidising agent. Ferrous iron formed has been titrated as usual against a standard potassium dichromate solution.

A method of preparation of diphenylcarbazone by oxidising diphenylcarbazine with potassium persulphate in presence of ferric iron as catalyst has also been described.

Diphenylcarbazine is a well-known reagent for colorimetric detection and estimation of chromium(VI) (Mellan, "Organic Reagents in Inorganic Analysis", Blakiston Co., Philadelphia, 1941, p. 316). When a chromate solution is added to an acidified solution of diphenylcarbazine, a purple colour develops which, on addition of more chromate solution, begins to fade away; the colour finally disappears completely. The rate of colour development is moderately rapid, but that of disappearance is comparatively slow. Estimation of these two compounds by titration with a dichromate solution (end point being determined by the colour disappearance) has been found difficult due to slowness of the colour disappearance reaction, and no concordant results have been obtained.

Quantitative estimation has been found, however, to be possible using ferric iron as the oxidising agent. The oxidation reaction may be represented as:

(where RH_4 =diphenylcarbazine, RH_2 =diphenylcarbazone and R =diphenylcarbadiazone).

Ferrous iron thus formed can be titrated as usual with a standard dichromate solution.

$$\begin{aligned} 1 \text{ c.c. of } 0.01 \text{ N-} \text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 &\equiv \left(\frac{0.00242}{4} \right) \text{ g.} = 0.605 \text{ mg. of } \text{RH}_4 \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{0.00240}{2} \right) \text{ g.} = 1.20 \text{ mg. of } \text{RH}_2 \end{aligned}$$

As the reagents are generally used as solutions in ethanol or acetone, the interferences due to these solvents have also been studied. With ethanol higher values were obtained evidently due to partial oxidation of the solvent with chromic acid. But with acetone the values were lower unaccountably.

It is interesting to note here that diphenylcarbazone of A. R. quality from the market was found to be a mixture of diphenylcarbazine and carbazone. A sample after proper drying in vacuum over H_2SO_4 was found to contain only 17% of the latter.

EXPERIMENTAL

Diphenylcarbazine of A. R. quality was further purified by pouring hot ethanolic solution to a large volume of hot water. The first crop of crystals was collected, m.p. 172°.

Diphenylcarbazone was prepared from diphenylcarbazine (2g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (120 c.c.). The solution was diluted with $\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (40 c.c.) and to it a 10% solution (0.2 c.c.) of ferric alum was added. A solution of potassium persulphate (2.6 g.) in water (40 c.c.) was slowly added to the above mixture under vigorous stirring. It was allowed to stand for

30 minutes, diluted with ice-cold water and then extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed repeatedly with water till free of acetic acid. It was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On evaporation of the ether, crystals of diphenylcarbazone separated. It was recrystallised from ether, m.p. 126°, yield 1.2 g.

Glacial acetic acid and acetone were redistilled over chromic acid, and found free from chromic acid by testing with diphenylcarbazide. Other reagents used were of A.R. quality.

Procedure.—Diphenylcarbazide or diphenylcarbazone (known amount) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and the solution was diluted with acetic acid to a known volume. An aliquot of this solution was taken in a 250 c.c. conical flask and to it were added 20 c.c. of 10% solution of ferric alum in 2 *N*-H₂SO₄ and 5 c.c. of 4*N*-H₂SO₄. The mixture was allowed to stand for 7 minutes or till the red tint disappeared. Phosphoric acid (syrupy, 5. c.c.) and 5 drops of 0.5% aqueous solution of barium diphenylaminesulphonate were added to the above mixture, which was titrated with a standard dichromate solution. In the estimation of ferrous iron, the acid strength should be maintained between 1 *N* and 2 *N*. Results are recorded in Table I (A and B).

The interference of this two solvents has also been studied (Table II). Results obtained from diphenylcarbazone from the market are shown in Table III.

TABLE I

Amount taken.	Aliquot titrated.	0.01 <i>N</i> -K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ reqd.	Amount.		Error.
			Present.	Found.	
A. Diphenylcarbazide, dissolved in 50 c.c. of acetic acid.					
60.0 mg	6 c.c.	12.00 c.c.	7.20 mg.	7.26 mg.	÷ 0.06 mg.
"	4	8.00	4.80	4.84	÷ 0.04
60.6	5	10.05	6.06	6.08	+ 0.02
"	10	20.00	12.12	12.10	- 0.02
B. Diphenylcarbazone, dissolved in 50 c.c. of acetic acid.					
51.4	10	8.70	10.28	10.44	÷ 0.16
"	15	13.00	15.42	15.60	÷ 0.18
60.4	10	10.20	12.08	12.24	÷ 0.16
"	5	5.10	6.04	6.12	- 0.08

TABLE II

Diphenylcarbazide taken (0.1210 g.), dissolved in 100 c.c. of acetic acid. An aliquot of 10 c.c. was taken for each titration.

Solvent added.	0.01 <i>N</i> -K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ reqd.	Amount.		Error.
		Present.	Found.	
A. Solvent : ethanol.				
0 c.c.	20.00 c.c.	12.10 mg.	12.10 mg.	± 0.00 mg.
1	20.30	12.10	12.28	+ 0.18
2	21.00	12.10	12.70	+ 0.60
5	21.90	12.10	13.25	+ 1.15
10	23.00	12.10	13.92	+ 1.82
B. Solvent : acetone.				
0	20.00	12.10	12.10	± 0.00
2	19.95	12.10	12.07	- 0.03
5	19.90	12.10	12.04	- 0.06
10	19.85	12.10	12.00	- 0.10
15	19.85	12.10	12.00	- 0.10

TABLE III

Diphenylcarbazono (A. R. from the market) taken=0.0603g. (dissolved in 50 c.c. of acetic acid).

Aliquot titrated.	0.01N-K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ reqd.	Material taken.	Carbazone found.	
6 c.c.	10.95 c.c.	7.24 mg.	1.23 mg.	17.04%
10	18.30	12.06	1.99	16.57
15	27.40	18.09	3.05	16.86

The results obtained in the case of diphenylcarbazono were slightly higher than the theoretical (Table I, B). This might be due to the presence of a small amount of diphenylcarbazono in the sample, which could not be removed by recrystallisation.

Diphenylcarbazono and diphenylcarbazono are used in detecting various metal ions due to the formation of coloured compounds. In these compounds the reagents may be present either as carbazono or carbazono or both. These may possibly be estimated by the method outlined above. Moreover, the purity of diphenylcarbazono may also be found out.

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Received September 21, 1959.